

UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM

Navigating Digital Sanctuaries: An In-Depth Analysis of Social Dynamics in Mental Health Subreddits

Media and Information, New Media

Bachelor Thesis

By
Martin Hadzhiev

Abstract

This thesis explores the intricate dynamics of social interaction, anonymity, and collective identity within mental health-related subreddits (r/Anxiety, r/mentalhealth, r/depression) and their contribution to community building and social support. Implementing a constructivist grounded theory approach mixed with qualitative content analysis, this study delves into the role of Reddit's platform features in shaping discussions, the emergence of collective identities, and the pivotal role of moderation. The findings reveal that these subreddits not only function as platforms for information and support but also evolve into digital sanctuaries where communal empathy, shared identity, and mutual support thrive. This research highlights the potential of such online communities in offering alternative avenues for mental health support, while also acknowledging the challenges and risks inherent in digital mental health discourse. The insights contribute significantly to the understanding of media-specific aspects in online mental health communities, with implications for users, mental health professionals, and policymakers.

Contents

1. Introduction	3
1.1 The Rising Importance of Online Mental Health Communities	3
1.2 Aim and Scope of the Research	4
1.3 Theoretical Framework and Methodological Approach	5
2. Literature Review	7
2.1 Methodological Approaches: Qualitative Content Analysis and Grounded Theory	7
2.2 Moderation, Communication, and Community Support in Online Mental Health Forums	9
3. Methodology	11
3.1 Selection of Subreddits	11
3.2 Comparative Analysis Across Subreddits	11

3.3 Ethical Considerations in Data Collection	12
3.4 Methodological Framework: Qualitative Content Analysis and Grounded Theory	12
3.5 Decoding Discourse: Inside the Codebook	13
4. Analysis	17
4.1 Interface and affordances of Reddit	17
4.2 Decoding Dialogue in r/depression	19
4.3 Decoding Dialogue in r/Anxiety	23
4.4 Decoding Dialogue in r/mentalhealth	26
4.5 Moderation Practices	30
4.6 Comparative dynamics	32
5. Discussion	35
5.1 Comparative Cultural Dynamics across Subreddits	35
5.2 Moderation and Implications for Digital Mental Health Discourse	35
6. Conclusion	36
6.1 Synthesis of Online Mental Health Community Dynamics	36
6.2 Future Trajectories and Implications for Mental Health Support	37
7. Bibliography	37
8. Appendix	40

1. Introduction

1.1 The Rising Importance of Online Mental Health Communities

In the age of digital transformation, where information and interpersonal connections are available at our fingertips, mental health continues to emerge as a pressing societal concern. The escalating prevalence of mental health issues beckons a significant paradigm shift: individuals are increasingly turning to online platforms as reservoirs for support, knowledge, and communal engagement (Choudhury & De 2014; Pretorius et al. 2019). It is within this burgeoning digital nexus that Reddit, a vast online community, serves as a particularly vibrant forum for mental health discourse.

Take, for instance, Alex, a 30-year-old grappling with anxiety. Uncomfortable with traditional therapeutic settings and inhibited from discussing his fears with his immediate social circle, Alex ventures into Reddit's mental health-related subreddits. Here, he finds an unexpected sanctuary. After sharing a candid post about his latest anxiety attack, Alex receives a flurry of responses—ranging from empathetic nods to practical coping strategies—all conveying a resonant understanding.

Alex's experience is not an isolated one; it threads into a larger tapestry of digital narratives that are interwoven daily on Reddit's mental health-focused communities. This emergent form of community, mediated through Reddit's specific platform features, necessitates scholarly attention.

1.2 Aim and Scope of the Research

This thesis investigates the intricate dynamics of social interaction, anonymity, and collective identity within Reddit's mental health-related subreddits and how these contribute to community building and social support. The social and political relevance of this research project cannot be understated, especially in an era where digital discourse is deeply entwined with societal well-being and policy frameworks (Luo & Hancock 2020). The virtual spaces within Reddit's mental health-related subreddits are not merely forums for personal expression, but also sites of collective identity formation and socio-political dialogue (Prakasam & Huxtable-Thomas 2021).

The conversations nestled within these digital communities often reflect, and sometimes challenge, broader societal norms and stigmas associated with mental health. By facilitating discussions around mental health in a relatively anonymous setting, these online platforms can potentially foster destigmatization, augment public understanding, and even inform mental health policies (Saha et al. 2020). This highlights the necessity and societal relevance of examining the dynamics within such online communities.

Central to this exploration is the primary research question: "How do online platforms, particularly Reddit's mental health-related subreddits, facilitate community building, social support, and navigate challenges associated with mental health discourse?"

This question serves as the guiding beacon for this investigation, seeking to unravel the complex interplay between individual and collective experiences in these digital spaces, and how they are influenced by the platform's unique features.

This is further dissected in the sub-question: "What challenges and risks are associated with seeking or providing mental health support within online communities on Reddit, and how do users navigate these challenges?" While it may be secondary in focus, this question is indispensable for a well-rounded comprehension of the subject matter.

It examines the limitations tied to online mental health communities, thereby extending the scope from not only understanding the positive dynamics, but also identifying potential pitfalls and challenges. This dual approach gives the study a balanced view, making its conclusions both richer and more nuanced. The challenges unearthed through this question could have significant implications for platform moderation policies and could also inform the design of safer, more supportive online spaces for mental health discussions.

By investigating these interconnected research questions, this thesis has ambitious objectives within the rapidly expanding field of media studies, particularly where it overlaps with conversations about mental health in the digital realm. The goals of this research are multilayered.

On an academic level, it seeks to fill a noticeable gap in the existing literature around this topic. Most current research either focuses on mental health from a psychological perspective or explores online communities without diving into the unique characteristics and dynamics of mental health-related forums. This study aims to blend these areas by specifically examining how the features and tools provided by platforms like Reddit—such as upvoting systems, comment threads, and moderation policies—shape the way individuals interact, offer support, and form communities.

This gap is particularly noticeable in the exploration of how media-specific attributes such as platform affordances, moderation mechanisms, and the anonymity offered by platforms like Reddit contribute to the dynamics of online mental health communities. This study seeks to address this significant gap, thereby contributing to a more holistic understanding of digital mental health discourse within the broader academic landscape.

On a broader scale, this research aspires to extend its impact beyond the academic community. The insights gleaned from this study have the potential to inform public dialogue around mental health, breaking down stigmas and fostering a more nuanced understanding of online mental health communities.

Ultimately, at the core of this research endeavour are an array of pivotal concepts that not only form the intellectual infrastructure of this thesis, but also have broader implications in the domain of media studies and societal well-being. These key concepts include "community of support," "affordances," and "moderation".

1.3 Theoretical Framework and Methodological Approach

The concept of a "community of support" serves as the relational substrate of this study. In essence, it encapsulates the spirit of mutual assistance and shared identity among members of mental health-related subreddits (Giles & Newbold 2011). Its importance cannot be overstated, especially in an era where traditional forms of community are in flux and new forms of digital collectivism are on the rise.

Next, "affordances" refer to the functionalities and features intrinsic to Reddit as a platform, such as upvoting—a mechanism where users express approval or support for a post or comment, influencing its visibility and ranking—and commenting, that shape and enable specific kinds of user engagement (Prakasam & Huxtable-Thomas 2021). Understanding these affordances is critical because they fundamentally influence the dynamics of online interaction and communal building. They delineate what is possible and what is rewarded within these digital spaces, thereby setting the stage for how social support can be effectively rendered.

The concept of 'moderation' involves governance mechanisms in online spaces, including both automated algorithms and human overseers, called moderators (Huh, et al. 2016). These moderators enforce guidelines, manage content for relevance, and resolve conflicts, ensuring a respectful environment. In mental health subreddits, their role is crucial for maintaining a safe space for sensitive discussions. They engage with the community, stimulate discussions, and adapt policies to evolving needs. Moderators also respond to member reports and provide intervention in crises. This

investigation into moderation is essential for understanding its impact on conversation quality and participant safety, significantly affecting social support effectiveness in digital communities (Wise, Hamman, & Thorson 2006).

The database for this study is curated to delve into the dynamics of social interaction, anonymity, and collective identity within the mental health-centric subreddits of Reddit, specifically r/mentalhealth, r/Anxiety, and r/depression. Using a personalized python script, 20 of the most upvoted posts from each subreddit are selected, summing up to a total of 60 posts, complemented by an analysis of 478 comments, to unearth dominant community discourses. In addition to the textual content, metadata encompassing comment count and upvote numbers are included, presenting a multi-dimensional perspective on user engagement.

The layered insight gained from the meticulous compilation and analysis of this database provides a fertile ground for the ensuing qualitative content analysis. This approach is particularly suited for the nuanced, interpretative goals intrinsic to the field, allowing for a rich exploration of Reddit's complex textual and interactional landscape. The adaptability of qualitative content analysis enables the study to focus on both macro and micro-level phenomena—ranging from broad thematic categorizations to nuanced discourse analysis.

In this study, thematic analysis serves as an analytical framework to distill and categorize emergent patterns within the textual data gleaned from selected posts and comments on mental health-centric subreddits (Lester et al. 2020). This approach entails using a purposive sampling strategy to categorize posts and comments based on defined criteria which will be dissected in detail in the methodology section. Moreover, an examination of comments on these posts is conducted to unravel the dynamics of social support being offered and sought within these digital communities. Through this lens, a multifaceted exploration of these online interactions is undertaken, providing a comprehensive, current, and nuanced understanding of the supportive ecosystem within these digital communities.

In the subsequent chapters, this study unfolds systematically. The journey begins with a literature review that establishes the academic context and illuminates existing research pertinent to online mental health communities. This sets the stage for a thorough exploration of our methodology, detailing the approach and techniques used to analyze the selected mental health-related subreddits: r/anxiety, r/mentalhealth, and r/depression. The culmination of this process is a comprehensive qualitative analysis, delving deep into the social dynamics and support mechanisms within these digital communities.

2. Literature Review

As discussed in the previous chapter, the central quest of this study navigates the terrain of social dynamics, moderation practices, and collective identity manifestation within mental health-centric subreddits. Rooted in the broader societal discourse on mental health, this inquiry explores the digital configurations that shape community building and social support in online realms, specifically on the platform of Reddit (Choudhury & De, 2014). The social networks formed on this platform, underscored by the dynamics of user interactions and social tie strength, provide a rich context for analyzing the communal ethos and supportive frameworks emergent within these digital spheres (Xu & Zhang, 2016).

2.1 Methodological Approaches: Qualitative Content Analysis and Grounded Theory

In the exploration of online communities, particularly within mental health discourse on platforms like Reddit, Grounded Theory (GT) and Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA) present themselves as pivotal methodologies. The development of GT, as initiated by Barney G. Glaser and Anselm L. Strauss in 1967, marked a significant shift in qualitative research methods. It introduced an inductive approach where theories are developed directly from the data, making it especially effective for studying emergent phenomena within digital landscapes, like mental health discussions on social media platforms.

Grounded Theory (GT), as conceptualized by Glaser and Strauss, represents an intricate dance between inductive reasoning and empirical saturation. It is a research strategy that prizes the discovery of theory from within the data itself, eschewing preconceived hypotheses for theories that emerge through the researcher's engagement with the research context (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). This methodological approach is characterized by its iterative cycles of data collection and analysis, with the constant comparative method at its core, ensuring that theoretical developments are deeply rooted in the data's empirical foundations.

Charmaz's (2006) Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) extends this foundational approach by emphasizing the co-constructive nature of knowledge creation, where the researcher's insights and the participants' experiences are interwoven to form theory. CGT acknowledges the subjective involvement of the researcher, advocating for reflexivity in the interpretation of data and the shaping of emergent theory (Charmaz, 2006). This reflexivity is not seen as a bias to be eliminated but as an integral part of the research process that adds depth and context to the theory being developed.

In addressing criticisms of Grounded Theory (GT), it is important to consider two prevalent misconceptions identified by Timonen et al. (2018). The first criticism is the perceived requirement for GT to invariably produce a fully developed theory. This notion, stemming from the expectation that GT should result in a comprehensive system of ideas capable of explaining and predicting phenomena, can be daunting, especially for less experienced researchers. However, this expectation overlooks the inherent flexibility of GT. In practice, GT often leads to greater conceptual clarity or the creation of a conceptual framework, which may not constitute a fully elaborated theory in the traditional sense (Timonen et al., 2018). This flexibility is one of GT's strengths, accommodating a range of theoretical outcomes based on the research scope and data nature. Recognizing that the journey towards understanding and explaining phenomena can be as valuable as the production of a comprehensive theory is crucial.

The second criticism concerns the idea that engaging with existing literature prior to data collection undermines the integrity of GT. While classical grounded theorists like Glaser and Strauss initially recommended against this engagement, this approach has been reconsidered in light of modern research practices. Charmaz (2014) is among those who have critiqued the notion of the researcher as a "blank slate," arguing that such a stance is no longer realistic or practical. In today's academic settings, familiarity with existing literature is commonly a prerequisite. Timonen et al. (2018) further contend that engaging with literature can be advantageous for GT research. This engagement allows researchers to place their work within the broader scholarly context, aiding in the identification of gaps in existing knowledge and the refinement of research questions. Far from diminishing the theory's groundedness, this method provides a richer background against which new insights are viewed. Thus, integrating a literature review with GT can lead to a more nuanced understanding of data, building upon existing knowledge while remaining open to new discoveries.

Therefore, these criticisms, rather than highlighting weaknesses in GT, actually misinterpret its core principles. The method's adaptability in outcomes and the advantageous integration of existing literature underscore the depth and relevance of GT in contemporary research.

GT's strength lies in its ability to generate theory through a meticulous process of data collection and analysis, allowing for a deep understanding of complex social interactions (Bryant and Charmaz 2007; Martin et al. 2018). The evolution of Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) by Charmaz adds further depth to this methodology, emphasizing the co-constructive nature of knowledge and accommodating the dynamic nature of online communities.

Contrastingly, QCA, as illustrated by Pfeil and Zaphiris (2010), offers a structured approach for dissecting the textual richness of online forums, making it an essential tool for unearthing thematic insights and patterns within digital interactions. Choudhury and De's (2014) exploration into the discourse of mental health on Reddit demonstrates how QCA can reveal the intricacies of self-disclosure, social support, and anonymity, crucial elements in understanding the dynamics of online mental health communities.

Further cementing the relevance of QCA, Lester, Cho, & Lochmiller (2020) emphasize its utility in identifying and analyzing thematic patterns across language-based data. This systematic yet adaptable approach to thematic analysis proves invaluable in examining the nuanced social dynamics and support mechanisms within mental health-related subreddits. The synergy of QCA and thematic analysis aligns seamlessly with the objective of delving into the textual depth and contextual dimensions shaping online dialogues within these communities.

The interplay of GT and QCA in this study allows for a multidimensional examination of online discourse, combining the detailed textual analysis of QCA with the inductive theorization of GT. This methodological amalgamation is particularly potent for probing the complex nexus of social interactions, digital media, and mental health discourse on Reddit (Dai & Shi 2022; Van Der Nagel and Frith 2015).

Reddit's affordance of anonymity is a critical aspect of its appeal, especially in discussions around sensitive topics like mental health. Choudhury and De (2014) note that this anonymity facilitates self-disclosure, fostering a compassionate community environment. However, this study reveals that anonymity's influence may be more implicit than expected, rooted in a broader internet culture of ubiquitous anonymity, subtly shaping user interactions and community norms within these subreddits.

This aspect raises intriguing questions about the degree to which anonymity directly influences the communal ethos within mental health subreddits. Furthermore, the anonymity afforded by Reddit enables the construction and expression of online identities, often distinct from users' offline selves (Van Der Nagel & Frith, 2015).

2.2 Moderation, Communication, and Community Support in Online Mental Health Forums

The role of moderation is instrumental in maintaining the integrity and supportive nature of mental health communities on Reddit. Saha et al. (2020) underscore that effective moderation practices are integral to creating safe spaces for discourse, ensuring adherence to community guidelines, and mitigating harmful interactions. The proactive role of moderators, coupled with community-driven moderation enabled by Reddit's affordances, significantly contributes to the nurturing of supportive and respectful interactions within these communities.

While often neglected, the text-centric nature of Reddit affords a platform for nuanced expression and discussion. Park and Conway (2018) elucidate that the textual communication on Reddit enables individuals to articulate their mental health challenges intricately, thereby fostering a deeper understanding and engagement within the community.

However, this study proposes that the text-based format also comes with its own set of limitations, which have not been sufficiently addressed by Park and Conway (2018). In particular, the absence of non-verbal cues such as tone and facial expression can sometimes lead to misunderstandings or misinterpretations. Moreover, the focus on text may particularly deter individuals lacking sufficient literacy skills or proficiency in English from participating, given that these subreddits generally mandate communication exclusively in English. This could limit the diversity of voices and experiences, potentially excluding non-English speakers or those with lower literacy levels from contributing to the discourse within the subreddit. Thus, while textual communication facilitates nuanced discussions, it also introduces challenges that warrant further investigation.

Nonetheless, the confluence of Reddit's affordances adeptly facilitates the emergence of communities of support, providing a nurturing platform for individuals to engage in meaningful discourse and mutual support around shared experiences and challenges.

Based on the work of Dai and Shi (2022), communities of support are characterized by a collective identity, rooted in shared interests or experiences, where individuals find a sense of belonging and validation. The sense of empathy and understanding within the community forms a supportive network that helps individuals cope with various challenges, whether they are medical, emotional, or related to specific situations. Central to these communities is the establishment of empathetic connections, where individuals feel seen, heard, and validated. The communal bond is further cemented by a shared interest or purpose, providing a common ground for interaction and support (Hammond 2015).

The digital landscape, with its unique features, significantly boosts the potential of support communities. Platforms like Reddit, offering anonymity, self-disclosure, and community moderation, foster supportive interactions and transcend physical distances (Choudhury and De 2017). This is key for connecting individuals who feel isolated, as they can join communities, regardless of location. These connections bring diverse perspectives, enriching the support network. Features like Reddit's

upvoting system also enhance these communities by highlighting relevant discussions, fostering a supportive culture where the community collectively assesses the value of shared information.

While online platforms provide the foundational elements that allow communities to form, effective moderation is crucial for these communities to thrive and maintain a healthy discourse (Skousen et al., 2020). This is particularly true in the context of online mental health communities. Designed as spaces for individuals to interact, seek advice, and share experiences concerning mental health, the role of moderation within these settings becomes pivotal. It serves as the bedrock for ensuring a safe and nurturing environment, especially given the sensitive nature of mental health discussions. As Saha et al. (2020) contend, effective moderation safeguards individuals who are particularly vulnerable to antisocial behaviors such as online harassment or abuse, thereby sustaining the supportive ethos of these communities.

The presence of a moderator significantly enhances discourse quality in online forums. Moderation increases user engagement, encourages open expression of emotions, and minimizes undesirable behaviors (Wise et al. 2006). Moderators are key in facilitating peer support, steering conversations constructively, and ensuring discussions remain beneficial and safe.

Moderation fosters linguistic coordination, building trust crucial for mental health support. Moderators' roles, including discipline-keeping and counseling, help define community norms and align with Reddit's guidelines, ensuring civil discussions that reflect community values (Skousen et al., 2020).

Much of the literature on online mental health communities highlights the crucial role of moderation in maintaining a supportive and structured environment. However, there's a notable gap when it comes to recognizing the efforts of moderators, who are often volunteers. As Rayland and Andrews' (2023) work demonstrates, moderators often work tirelessly to manage discussions and ensure the well-being of community members, but at the potential cost of their own mental health.

Despite their essential role in shaping the community and maintaining a supportive environment, the literature rarely addresses the unique challenges and well-being of moderators. These individuals balance significant responsibilities, from steering conversations to managing conflicts, all without formal compensation. The emotional impact of this volunteer work remains largely unexplored, marking a gap in current research.

Addressing this gap could provide a more complete understanding of online mental health communities, shedding light on the sustainability and resilience of these platforms. While this paper does not delve into the mental health consequences for moderators, it's an essential aspect to bear in mind when researching online communities, as it significantly contributes to the broader understanding and dynamics of digital support ecosystems.

Moderation practices, like instructive strategies, are crucial for maintaining constructive interactions and civility in online patient communities (Skousen et al., 2020). The interplay of effective moderation and text-based interactions shapes collective identity and empathy in Reddit's mental health forums. The next section transitions to the methodological approach, focusing on the selection of subreddits to examine social dynamics and identity formation.

3. Methodology

3.1 Selection of Subreddits

This research delves into the dynamics of social interaction, moderation, and collective identity within specific mental health-related subreddits: r/mentalhealth, r/Anxiety, and r/depression. The previous chapter highlighted the relevance of these communities for the study. In this section, the focus shifts towards the methodological decisions and their underlying rationale. The selection of these subreddits was informed by their substantial user base and active engagement in mental health discussions. Originating between 2008 and 2009, they have grown exponentially, with memberships as of September 2023 reaching over 900,000 in r/depression, 630,000 in r/Anxiety, and 421,000 in r/mentalhealth. The selection of these specific subreddits reflects a deliberate aim to venture into spaces where mental health dialogues are actively pursued by a substantial user base. This vast membership accentuates a pronounced need and interest in online spaces where individuals can traverse the challenging terrain of mental health issues (Xu and Zhang 2016).

Building on this foundation, it is pertinent to specifically focus on a preliminary phase of examination: a short and concise interface analysis of the r/mentalhealth subreddit homepage. This subreddit was chosen for this initial step due to its more detailed and informative homepage compared to r/Anxiety and r/depression, making it particularly suitable for such analysis. This analysis serves a dual purpose. Firstly, it situates the digital environment of these communities, highlighting how the design and structure of Reddit potentially influence user engagement and interaction patterns. Secondly, it provides essential insight into user navigation and content accessibility within these forums, crucial for interpreting the context and relevance of the subsequent qualitative content analysis. Thus, this interface analysis acts as a gateway to a deeper understanding of the social dynamics and community building within these mental health-related subreddits.

3.2 Comparative Analysis Across Subreddits

In addition to individual subreddit analysis, this research employs comparative analysis to examine the interplay and differences between r/mentalhealth, r/anxiety, and r/depression. This approach is crucial for a holistic understanding of mental health discourse across various communities. It reveals unique characteristics and shared challenges within these virtual support networks, enhancing our understanding of community dynamics. By comparing conversation themes, user engagements, and moderation practices across subreddits, we identify patterns specific to online mental health discussions and particular conditions. This method uncovers the deeper structures of support and interaction, offering insights into the scalability of online support and the applicability of moderation practices. Comparative analysis thus enriches our understanding of community building and social

support efficacy in digital spaces, informing future digital mental health initiatives and platform governance policies.

The later half of this chapter will offer a detailed dissection and review of the codebook used in the analysis. This will include an in-depth exploration of the purposive sampling strategy, elucidating its significance and the rationale behind its adoption in this research context. However, it's important to establish the foundational methodology and ethical considerations of this research first.

3.3 Ethical Considerations in Data Collection

This research was conducted with a strong commitment to ethical principles, particularly regarding user privacy and data sensitivity. Prior to data collection, permission was sought and obtained from the moderators of the selected subreddits through Reddit's private chat function. The moderators stipulated conditions to protect user anonymity and avoid any form of user criticism. In compliance, no usernames or identifiable personal information were collected. The study was designed to respect the inherent trust users place in these platforms, using the data exclusively for academic purposes and avoiding any potential harm to the subreddit communities.

3.4 Methodological Framework: Qualitative Content Analysis and Grounded Theory

As mentioned in the literature review section, this research employs Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA) and Grounded Theory (GT). QCA is crucial for uncovering the intricate interactions and themes in online forums. It provides a structured yet adaptable framework for analyzing textual data rich in context and emotion. Pfeil & Zaphiris (2010) highlight QCA's effectiveness in extracting themes from online discussions. Its ability to identify trends, discourse styles, and emerging topics enhances its suitability for analyzing dialogues within Reddit's mental health communities.

Expanding on the foundational principles of QCA, this study meticulously applies its techniques to the selected posts and comments from the mental health-related subreddits. The emphasis is on a deeper, more granular analysis of the content, ensuring that every facet of the textual data is explored.

To ensure the data collected is both representative and insightful, a purposive sampling strategy was employed. This sampling strategy is a non-probability sampling technique where specific criteria, informed by the research objectives, guide the selection of the sample. This method is particularly useful when researchers aim to capture insights from a specific subset of a population that can provide rich and relevant information on the topic of interest (Tongco 2007). In the context of this study, the purposive sampling strategy was employed to select the most upvoted posts across the mental health-related subreddits. This decision was based on the rationale that such posts, having garnered significant community attention, would be indicative of prevailing discourses and sentiments within these online communities.

In the actual application of QCA, each post and comment undergoes a multi-layered analysis. Beyond the explicit messages, there's an exploration of the nuances, the undertones, and the latent themes that might be interwoven within the text. This involves not just understanding what is being said, but also discerning why it's being said, and the broader implications it might have within the context of the subreddit and the mental health discourse at large.

The iterative nature of the QCA process in this study ensures that the analysis is both adaptive and comprehensive. As more data is scrutinized, initial findings are continually refined, ensuring that the

insights derived are both robust and reflective of the complexities of the data. This depth of analysis, coupled with the methodological rigor of QCA, provides a holistic understanding of the narratives, interactions, and dynamics within the selected mental health-related subreddits.

While QCA offers a structured approach to analyzing textual content, Grounded Theory (GT) provides a complementary framework for inductively generating theory from the data. This methodological paradigm, introduced by sociologists Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss in their seminal book "The Discovery of Grounded Theory" (1967), marked a significant departure from the positivist tradition, enabling researchers to develop theories grounded in empirical observations.

The academic dialogue surrounding GT has since evolved, with a prominent critique emerging from the Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) posited by Kathy Charmaz (2006, 140). Unlike classical GT, CGT emphasizes the interpretive authority of the researcher and the co-construction of meaning between researcher and participant. This approach foregrounds the interpretative lenses through which data is viewed, enriching the discourse on methodological rigor and epistemological stance in GT.

For this study, CGT was chosen due to its alignment with the research objectives, particularly its emphasis on the intricate social interactions, moderation, and collective identity within mental health-related subreddits. The interpretive lens of CGT facilitates a deeper understanding of the subjective experiences and social realities of individuals within these online communities. Furthermore, the methodological robustness of CGT ensures a grounded, inductive, and iterative engagement with the data, providing a structured yet adaptable framework to navigate the complex social dynamics within these digital realms.

The digital realm of mental health subreddits is characterized by dynamic interactions where meanings are actively constructed and negotiated. Given the sensitive nature of mental health discussions, the reflexive nature of CGT, which acknowledges the influence of the researcher's perspectives and biases, ensures that the analysis remains both empathetic and critically engaged. In essence, while classical GT offers a foundational approach, the advantages of CGT, with its interpretive depth and co-constructive approach, make it a more fitting choice for this research.

Having established the foundational methodology and ethical considerations of this research, it is imperative to delve deeper into the granular aspects of data analysis. The subsequent section will provide a comprehensive dissection of the codebook, elucidating the thematic codes applied to both posts and comments. This detailed breakdown will offer insights into the diverse facets of discourse within these mental health subreddits, from the nature of the posts to the nuances of community interactions.

3.5 Decoding Discourse: Inside the Codebook

In qualitative research, a codebook serves as a pivotal tool that delineates the coding framework, defining and categorizing thematic elements within the dataset. It ensures consistency, clarity, and systematicity in the data analysis process (Saldaña, 2015, 41). By providing a comprehensive overview of the coding framework, the aim is to offer transparency in the analytical process and ensure the rigor and consistency of findings within the mental health subreddits.

Importantly, a 'code' is a binary thematic label applied to qualitative data, indicating the presence or absence of specific elements within posts and comments, such as 'Humor and Satire' or 'Emotional

Disclosure'. Conversely, a 'variable' represents a broader, non-binary category of analysis, such as 'Tone' or 'Emotional tone and language', which can vary in nature and is not limited to a binary presence or absence. This distinction allows for a nuanced analysis of the data, capturing both specific thematic occurrences and broader, variable trends.

The study encompasses six datasets. The initial three datasets comprise the 20 most upvoted posts from each subreddit, encapsulating the following columns:

1. **Upvotes:** A measure of community engagement and resonance. High upvotes indicate topics of significant interest or concern within the community.
2. **Timestamp:** Provides context regarding when the post was made, in order to make sure that the post falls within the temporal scope of this research
3. **Content:** The core textual data, offering insights into the user's concerns, experiences, and perspectives.
4. **URL:** The URL is essential for post verification as it provides direct access to the original content, ensuring the analysis remains accurate and authentic. If a post is deleted by a user or moderator, the URL helps determine its current status, underscoring the importance of respecting ethical standards. Additionally, it establishes accountability by tracing analyses back to their source and allows for deeper exploration, offering more context around the post. In short, the URL is a key tool for maintaining authenticity, ethics, and understanding in online discussions.
5. **Comment_Count:** An indicator of community engagement and discussion intensity around the post.

The selection of specific columns like title, content, upvotes, timestamp, URL, and comment count goes beyond data collection; it aims to comprehensively represent each post within its digital context. This research captures both the individual narrative and its wider community resonance. This approach, spanning from personal experiences to collective community engagement, enables a nuanced understanding. Essentially, these columns are chosen to connect individual expression with collective reception in mental health subreddits.

Following the establishment of the initial three datasets, each post is then meticulously analyzed using specific thematic codes derived from the columns described. These themes and codes serve as the foundation for understanding the nuances of each post and facilitate a systematic approach to data interpretation.

1. **Initiation of Dialogue:** These posts aim to foster community discussions, reflecting users' desire for engagement and understanding.

2. **Humor and Satire:** Posts which include any type of humor or satire. This code serves for Highlighting the community's use of humor as a coping mechanism, offering insights into alternative ways of addressing mental health.
3. **Celebratory Posts:** These posts underscore the community's supportive nature, celebrating individual milestones and victories.
4. **Emotional Disclosure:** Posts that serve as a testament to the trust and safety users feel within the subreddit, allowing for open emotional discussions.
5. **Help-Seeking Barriers:** Posts reflecting the real-world challenges users face in seeking professional mental health support.
6. **Treatment and Therapy Queries:** Indicative of the community's role as a resource for mental health information and advice.
7. **Solution-Oriented vs. Venting:** This code distinguishes between posts seeking advice and those primarily serving as emotional outlets.

Having detailed the thematic coding applied to the posts, it is equally imperative to explore the comments accompanying these posts. Comments, much like posts, offer a rich tapestry of community sentiments, reactions, and discourses. In this vein, the study delved deep into the analysis of comment themes.

Figure 1. Comparative User Base of Mental Health-Related Subreddits

In the analysis of comment themes, a total of 562 individual comments were examined, distributed across the three subreddits as follows: 236 in r/depression, 193 in r/Anxiety, and 133 in r/mentalhealth. It is noteworthy that the volume of comments varies across these subreddits. This variation can be attributed to the differential membership sizes of the subreddits (*Figure 1*). To ensure a balanced and comparative analysis across these subreddits, the study will employ percentages when discussing themes. This approach facilitates a relative perspective, emphasizing proportional representation rather than absolute numbers, thereby providing a more nuanced understanding of the discourse across the subreddits.

To guide the analysis and categorization of comment themes, the following list of codes has been developed. These codes serve as a structured framework for identifying and interpreting recurring patterns and topics within the comments. Each code represents a specific aspect of the subreddit discussions and contributes to a comprehensive analysis of user interactions and experiences.

1. **External Influences:** Comments about broader societal events or figures and how those influences might impact the users' mental and emotional wellbeing
2. **Empathetic Language:** A measure of the community's supportive and understanding nature.
3. **Expressions of Anonymity:** Instances highlighting the value users place on privacy and anonymity.
4. **Story Sharing:** Reflecting the community's desire to share personal experiences, fostering mutual understanding.
5. **Resilience and Coping Strategies:** Comments offering insights into how users can navigate mental health challenges.
6. **Stigmatization:** Instances of comments which address and/or combat mental health stigmatization.
7. **Resource Sharing:** Comments which provide valuable resources for mental health information and support.
8. **Validation:** Moments where users validate and affirm each other's experiences, underscoring the community's supportive nature.
9. **Moderation and Rules Adherence:** Instances in which users highlight the role of subreddit governance in shaping and guiding discussions.

10. **Tone:** This variable focuses on identifying and categorizing the emotional tone of posts and comments within the subreddit. It involves classifying the language used as optimistic, pessimistic, neutral, or other emotional tones. This variable reveals patterns in how different tones correlate with user engagement (e.g., likes, replies) and the nature of responses received. For instance, an optimistic post might attract more encouraging comments, while a pessimistic one might draw more empathetic responses. Understanding these dynamics can provide valuable insights into how the emotional tone of a post or comment influences the type and level of community interaction and support.

11. **Top 3 Most Frequent Keywords:** This variable provides a snapshot of the main themes in the comments. In this study, 'keywords' are terms or phrases summarizing themes in comments, chosen for their frequency and relevance to the research goals. They reflect the mental health discourse in the subreddits. Using three keywords per comment, instead of one, captures multiple themes in each comment, acknowledging its complexity. Keywords deepen the analysis and enable comparison across posts and subreddits, uncovering trends and community concerns. This approach ensures a comprehensive and authentic representation of the multifaceted discussions in mental health communities.

As we transition into the analysis section, we will unravel the thematic intricacies, exploring the diverse facets of discourse, from the nature of the posts to the subtleties of community interactions. The subsequent analysis aims to shed light on the multifaceted layers of communication, support, and identity within these digital mental health communities.

4. Analysis

4.1 Interface and affordances of Reddit

In dissecting the digital landscape of Reddit, particularly within the r/mentalhealth community, we commence by peeling back the layers of the platform's interface and core features—a critical step in understanding the user experience and subsequent social dynamics. The homepage of r/mentalhealth stands as a gateway, not only to the community but also to the intricate web of affordances that shape user behavior. These affordances—interactive elements that facilitate certain actions while constraining others—remain constantly present, accompanying the user's navigation through the subreddit and thus providing a stable framework for interactions and communicative practices.

Figure 2. Overview of the features and interface of r/mentalhealth

A key affordance is the 'search by post flair' option, which allows users to navigate the vast ocean of content to find posts that resonate with their immediate emotional needs or inquiries (Figure 2-1). This feature not only structures content accessibility but also subtly influences the communal dialogue by highlighting certain types of interactions—whether individuals are seeking resources, wishing to share good news, or in dire need of support.

The subreddit's rules, delineated on the sidebar, function as a compass for user conduct, explicitly stating what is permissible within the community's digital walls (Figure 2-2). These guidelines are instrumental in fostering a safe space for open dialogue, as they stipulate the bounds of respect, privacy, and support that are hallmarks of the subreddit's ethos.

Adjacent to the rules, a list of 'other helpful subreddits' serves as signposts to related communities, recognizing the complex and multifaceted nature of mental health (*Figure 2-3*). This not only facilitates user navigation in the broader Reddit ecosystem but also underscores the interconnectedness of support networks online.

The 'moderators' section, subtle yet significant, represents the human element behind the digital interface (*Figure 2-4*). All 3 subreddits contain this component, with r/anxiety and r/mentalhealth displaying a list of 10 moderators, and r/mentalhealth displaying 5 moderators. This discrepancy can be attributed to the varying membership sizes of these subreddits.

While often overlooked, the description component of subreddits is a significant element that encapsulates the ethos and culture of these virtual communities. Descriptions serve as an informative yet concise prologue to their individual cultures and the user experiences they foster.

These descriptions, while brief, are potent indicators of the communities' intentions and ethos. They reflect the affordances of Reddit, which facilitate user-driven content curation within a semi-anonymous environment, allowing for a nuanced form of communal interaction that is shaped by democratic content visibility through upvotes and downvotes.

Typically, each subreddit's description delineates the boundaries of its community's discourse and sets the stage for the type and tone of interactions that are deemed appropriate. They act as filters, shaping the community by attracting individuals aligned with these outlined objectives and setting expectations for participation and support.

Ultimately, all these affordances and features are integral to user experience, permeating the platform consistently—both on homepages and within specific post interactions. This constancy ensures that the ethos of community and navigational ease are omnipresent, subtly guiding user conduct and fostering a culture of support and respect. Such design choices underpin community building, encouraging adherence to norms and facilitating moderation efforts by keeping guidelines and navigational aids always in sight.

As we delve deeper into the intricacies of Reddit's communities, we recognize that each community fosters its own unique form of interaction and dialogue. Moving forward, our analysis will focus on the nature of these interactions within specific communities, beginning with r/depression. This examination aims to uncover the patterns, themes, and dynamics of communication that define and characterize the engagement within this particular subreddit.

4.2 Decoding Dialogue in r/depression

This community, by its own description, provides 'Peer support for anyone struggling with a depressive disorder,' signalling its dedication to fostering a network of empathy and understanding. This academic inquiry centers on the posts and comments within the subreddit that collectively create a dynamic environment where individuals dealing with depression can share and reflect on their experiences. Here, the exchange of personal stories and emotional support is commonplace, offering a glimpse into the lived experiences of its members.

Figure 3. Distribution of Thematic Elements in r/depression Comments

The dominant themes of 'Story Sharing' (22.2%) and 'Empathetic Language' (19.6%) paint a picture of a community deeply engaged in personal narratives and supportive exchanges (Figure 3). The fact that 'Moderation' accounts for only 4% of the interactions hints at a self-regulating environment, with moderation being a subtle, albeit essential, influence on maintaining the subreddit's supportive culture.

Figure 4. Prevalence of pessimistic, neutral and optimistic comments among r/depression

The Distribution of pessimistic, neutral, and optimistic comments among r/depression showcases a predominance of pessimistic comments (53%), which may mirror the subreddit's primary function as a haven for those dealing with challenging emotional states (Figure 4). The presence of neutral (36%) and optimistic comments (11%) also suggests a balanced environment where hope and realism coexist with expressions of struggle.

Figure 5. Prevalent Keywords in r/depression Comments

Keywords such as 'Depression' (23.4%), 'Breakdown' (12.1%), and 'Feel' (10.5%) are frequently mentioned, indicating a focus on personal emotional states and the quest for understanding and connection (Figure 5). The mention of 'Therapy' (8.1%) and 'Meds (Medications)' (11.3%) underscores a proactive engagement with treatment and recovery within the community dialogue.

Figure 6. Thematic Trends in Posts across r/depression

With 'Emotional Disclosure' taking a significant share, there's an evident comfort in sharing personal stories, which corresponds with the high percentage of story-sharing and empathetic comments (Figure 6).

The interplay between 'Emotional Disclosure' in posts and 'Empathetic Language' in comments suggests a reciprocal relationship where vulnerability is met with compassion. Conversely, the 'Humor and Satire' and 'Celebratory Posts' components, though smaller, are vital, providing occasional relief and a reminder of the collective resilience present within the subreddit.

Connecting these insights, one can speculate that the prevalence of 'Story Sharing' and 'Empathetic Language' in comments may be a response to the need for connection and validation among members. The lower emphasis on 'Expressions of Anonymity' implies a community less concerned with privacy and more with sharing openly, possibly because the shared experience of depression already provides a sense of unity and anonymity.

The charts collectively illustrate r/depression as a community-centric platform where individuals not only seek empathy and understanding but are also met with a diverse range of responses from shared stories to practical advice on treatment. This multifaceted interaction suggests a balanced ecosystem where despite the prevalence of struggle, there is a continuous exchange of support, information, and occasionally, light-hearted content. The phenomenon observed here is a digital manifestation of community support, characterized by a tapestry of shared experiences, coping strategies, and moments of upliftment.

4.3 Decoding Dialogue in r/Anxiety

r/Anxiety is a community centered on "Discussion and support for sufferers and loved ones with anxiety conditions," encapsulating its mission to create a shared space for empathy, advice, and solidarity. This virtual haven extends its reach to "loved ones," highlighting a recognition of the collective impact of anxiety and the need for a supportive network that includes those who care for individuals with anxiety conditions. The subreddit not only fosters dialogue within its threads but also offers a link to a Discord server, a digital platform designed for creating communities with text, voice, and video communication capabilities (Chuan & Ratan, 2022), suggests an additional layer of real-time interaction and community building within r/anxiety. Participants are reminded to review the rules before posting, underscoring a commitment to maintaining a respectful and supportive environment for all members as they navigate the complexities of anxiety together.

Figure 7. Distribution of Thematic Elements in r/Anxiety Comments

The emphasis on 'Resilience and Coping Strategies' and 'Resource Sharing' within comments indicates a proactive exchange of personal strategies and resources, underscoring a strong communal commitment to mutual aid (Figure 7). As in the case of r/depression the low incidence of anonymity discussions might suggest that users trust the platform's privacy measures, allowing them to share openly without constantly addressing privacy concerns.

Figure 8. Thematic Trends in Posts across r/anxiety

The balance in the emotional tone of comments reflects an environment that accommodates a spectrum of emotional states, creating a space where optimism is welcome but not enforced, allowing for genuine sharing of individual struggles (Figure 8).

The community's active engagement is evident in the high percentage of posts initiating dialogue, suggesting that r/Anxiety is a starting point for many users' journeys in seeking advice or sharing their experiences. While 'Humor and Satire' are less prevalent, their presence indicates that humor is utilized as a coping mechanism, albeit not the central one.

Figure 9. Prevalence of pessimistic, neutral and optimistic comments among r/anxiety

Moreover, the distribution of emotional tones in r/Anxiety's comments invites a critical examination of the community's discourse dynamics. The preponderance of neutral comments may suggest a tendency towards objective discussion or a collective self-moderation in emotional expression (Figure 9). The substantial representation of both pessimistic and optimistic comments reflects the dual reality of anxiety experiences—oscillating between hope and despair. This distribution could signal a well-rounded community engagement, but it also raises questions about potential self-censorship or the community's response to expressions of negativity. The balance found here may indicate a supportive environment, yet it also poses an inquiry into how the community navigates and processes the complexities of mental health within a public forum.

Figure 10. Prevalent Keywords in r/Anxiety Comments

Keywords such as 'Treatment', 'Medication', and 'Therapist' dominate the conversations, highlighting the community's focus on actionable mental health strategies. The presence of 'Lonely' and 'Stressed' among these keywords paints a candid picture of the emotional triggers that bring users to the subreddit (Figure 10).

4.4 Decoding Dialogue in r/mentalhealth

r/mentalhealth positions itself as a welcoming and safe platform for open dialogue on mental health, extending a warm invitation with "Welcome! This is a safe place to discuss, vent, support, and share information about mental health, illness, and wellness." This subreddit is a collective endeavor, as the description emphasizes with "Together, we make this community great." It encourages active participation and a culture of respect and empathy, asking members to engage thoughtfully with one another. The community's ethos, as encapsulated in its self-description, is one of mutual support and shared growth, offering a compassionate space for individuals to explore and discuss the spectrum of mental health experiences.

Figure 11. Distribution of Thematic Elements in r/mentalhealth Comments

The community showcases a strong propensity for empathetic communication, which dominates the landscape of interactions. The significant prevalence of empathetic language in the comments indicates a culture where individuals feel heard and supported (*Figure 11*). This emphasis on empathy is further reinforced by the substantial volume of story-sharing, suggesting that personal narratives are not just welcomed but are a key component of the community's fabric.

Figure 12. Prevalence of pessimistic, neutral and optimistic comments among r/mentalhealth

The emotional tone within the subreddit paints a picture of a community grappling with complex emotions. Neutral and pessimistic comments outweigh the optimistic ones, likely mirroring the reality of many individuals' mental health experiences (Figure 12). This preponderance might suggest that while the community is a haven for support, it is also a repository for the raw, unvarnished realities of those facing mental health challenges.

Figure 13. Prevalent Keywords in r/mentalhealth Comments

Keywords like "Depression" and "Mental Health" are focal points, indicating not only the subject matter's seriousness but also possibly a demand for content that helps with understanding and navigating these conditions. The mention of "Suicide" and "Treatment" as frequent keywords highlights the critical nature of discussions and points to the subreddit's role as an emergency touchpoint for individuals seeking immediate advice or sharing urgent concerns (*Figure 13*).

Figure 14. Thematic Trends in Posts across r/mentalhealth

The high engagement in initiating dialogue suggests an active community where users are not passive consumers but contributors to a collective conversation. The overwhelming presence of emotional disclosure in posts indicates a trusted space for vulnerability, aligning with the community's empathetic communication style (Figure 14).

Interestingly, the presence of humor and celebratory posts, though less significant, implies that the community values a multifaceted approach to mental health discussions, allowing room for lighter moments and positive experiences.

4.5 Moderation Practices

The moderation practices among the subreddits are distinguished by their low intervention rates, with 4%, 7.5%, and 0.9% respectively. This minimal moderation could suggest that these communities inherently foster a healthy, self-regulating environment. The rarity of insults or disrespectful behavior might be indicative of quick and efficient moderation, albeit this remains difficult to quantify accurately due to the removal of comments by moderators, leaving no trace for analysis.

The absence of major disagreements in these communities, as observed in the discussions, doesn't necessarily imply a lack of conflict. It's plausible that conflicts, when they do arise, are swiftly addressed and removed by moderators, thus becoming invisible in the dataset. This theory is supported by the fact that, although comprehensive, the analysis couldn't account for the exact number of deleted posts, nor could it track the deletion of specific comments. Interestingly, some of the highly

upvoted posts that were deleted by moderators indicate a responsive moderation system that aligns with the community guidelines.

Figure 15. The most upvoted post on r/depression (As of September, 2023)

A notable example of moderation in r/depression is the subreddit's most upvoted post, authored by a moderator, that discourages private messaging among users (Figure 15). The post emphasizes the benefits of public interactions, including educating and helping a broader audience, and reducing the risk of over-dependence on individual helpers. This approach is grounded in concerns over compassion fatigue and the challenges of providing consistent, personal support in mental health contexts. The post also warns against potential exploitation by malevolent individuals targeting vulnerable users, underscoring the importance of community scrutiny in safeguarding members.

Figure 16. r/Anxiety rule against seeking and offering medical diagnoses

In the discourse analysis of r/Anxiety, it is intriguing to observe the prevalence of keywords such as 'Treatment', 'Medication', and 'Therapist'. Despite the general tendency in mental health forums, including r/Anxiety itself, to discourage discussions focused on medical treatments and medications,

these terms emerge as focal points. This paradoxical scenario in r/Anxiety, where conversations gravitate towards medical solutions despite the general discouragement of such discussions, may contribute to its comparatively high moderation rate of 7.5%. This rate stands out against r/depression (4%) and r/mentalhealth (0.9%).

The frequent inclusion of terms like 'Lonely' and 'Stressed' further enriches the narrative of the subreddit. These keywords not only reflect the emotional triggers for users to seek support but also hint at a dichotomy where the need for professional medical guidance is juxtaposed with the forum's normative stance against such discussions. This duality within r/Anxiety creates a complex landscape of interaction, blending the expression of emotional vulnerabilities with a cautious approach towards medical advice. Such a nuanced environment may necessitate a higher degree of moderation, ensuring a balance between supportive discourse and adherence to the community's guidelines on medical discussions (Figure 16).

In contrast, r/mentalhealth exhibits the lowest moderation rate, possibly due to its primary function as a platform for sharing stories and seeking empathy. The respectful and empathetic nature of interactions within this subreddit might stem from users identifying with each other's struggles, creating a naturally supportive environment that requires minimal moderation.

The diverse moderation practices across these subreddits significantly influence their social dynamics. In r/depression, the emphasis on public support over private messaging fosters a sense of community vigilance and collective responsibility. This approach likely enhances the visibility of support mechanisms, encouraging a culture of openness and shared learning. In r/anxiety, the stricter moderation on medical advice likely steers conversations towards more generalized support and shared experiences rather than specific medical guidance, which could be misleading or harmful. This careful moderation ensures that the platform remains a safe space for discussing anxiety without replacing professional medical advice.

Meanwhile, the low moderation in r/mentalhealth complements its role as a hub for empathetic exchanges and storytelling. The minimal intervention by moderators suggests a high degree of mutual respect and understanding among users, facilitating a self-sustaining environment of support and empathy.

4.6 Comparative dynamics

As this research has shown so far, the digital environments of r/Anxiety, r/depression, and r/mentalhealth on Reddit showcase a range of mental health discourses, each fostering unique interaction cultures that mirror their members' diverse needs. This analysis aims to intricately unravel the dialogues, emotional expressions, and community support mechanisms that characterize these subreddits. By scrutinizing the prevalent themes, emotional tones, and keyword frequencies, we delve into each subreddit's nuanced approach to mental health challenges, revealing the distinct forms of support and communal solidarity inherent to these online sanctuaries.

In r/anxiety, discussions are primarily centered around resilience, coping strategies, and resource sharing, reflecting a community actively engaging in mutual support and disseminating strategies for

managing anxiety. However, the minimal emphasis on anonymity suggests a potential oversight of deeper, more personal issues due to privacy concerns or the platform's public nature. This dynamic might result in surface-level engagements that fail to address deeper, underlying anxiety issues fully.

Contrastingly, r/depression is significantly shaped by story sharing and empathetic language use. These trends align with the introspective nature of depression, where sharing personal experiences serves as emotional release and seeking empathetic responses from a community that resonates with similar experiences. The prominence of stigmatization discussions may reflect the societal stigma associated with depression, encouraging users to seek validation and understanding. Critically, the high volume of pessimistic comments paints a picture of a community potentially burdened by collective sorrow, raising questions about the subreddit's ability to foster a supportive environment that balances empathy with constructive mental wellness pathways.

r/MentalHealth presents a more eclectic mix, with a significant portion of comments dedicated to validation and story sharing. This indicates a broad, inclusive approach where validating diverse mental health experiences and sharing personal narratives are at the community's core. Yet, the generalist nature of this subreddit could potentially lead to a lack of focused support for specific mental health conditions, raising questions about the depth and specificity of the community support provided.

The emotional tone in r/Anxiety, with its balanced distribution of pessimistic, neutral, and optimistic comments, suggests a community engaged in dynamic conversation about anxiety. However, this balance might also hint at a discourse that, while dynamic, may not fully delve into deeper, more complex anxiety-related issues. In contrast, r/depression's higher prevalence of pessimistic comments underscores the subreddit's alignment with the challenging nature of depression, where members frequently share their difficulties and seek support during low periods.

The keyword analysis across these subreddits tells a compelling narrative. r/Anxiety's focus on terms like 'Treatment' and 'Medication' highlights discussions centered on managing anxiety through medical intervention. In r/depression, the frequent mention of 'Depression', 'Breakdown', and 'Therapy' suggests a community deeply immersed in discussing depression intricacies, including acute episodes and pursuing professional help. r/MentalHealth's diverse keyword range, including 'Depression', 'Treatment', and 'Suicide', points to a community engaged in serious conversations encompassing a broad spectrum of mental health issues, from treatment options to addressing suicidal thoughts.

In r/Anxiety, the trend towards initiating dialogue, coupled with the presence of humor and satire, suggests a community using communication and levity as coping mechanisms. This approach might overshadow deeper, unaddressed concerns. r/depression, characterized by a strong inclination towards emotional disclosure and venting, serves as a vital outlet for depressive experiences. However, the prevalence of such posts raises concerns about the potential for echo chambers of despair without adequate pathways to recovery.

Figure 17. Solution-Oriented and Venting Posts among r/depression, r/Anxiety and r/mentalhealth

In examining the content dynamics across r/Anxiety, r/mentalhealth, and r/depression, as illustrated in Figure 17, a prominent trend emerges: venting posts significantly dominate in all three subreddits. While r/Anxiety maintains a somewhat balanced distribution between posts seeking practical mental health solutions and those centered on emotional expression and personal stories, the scale tips noticeably towards venting. Similarly, r/mentalhealth shows a clear inclination towards venting, emphasizing a community ethos that cherishes empathy and the cathartic value of sharing personal struggles and experiences.

This trend is even more pronounced in r/depression, where the majority of posts are characterized by emotional catharsis, underscoring a preference for using the platform as a space for expressing emotions rather than actively seeking solutions to specific problems. This overarching pattern of venting across the three forums highlights a fundamental aspect of these online communities, pointing to the need for moderation and support strategies that acknowledge and address the predominant use of these spaces for emotional release and support.

This analysis has shed light on the distinct dynamics and potential limitations present in how each subreddit addresses mental health needs. r/anxiety primarily facilitates practical discussions but tends to skim over deeper emotional aspects. Conversely, r/depression, while offering a supportive space, might inadvertently contribute to a narrative of despair. Similarly, r/MentalHealth's broad scope sometimes results in a lack of focused support for specific mental health issues. Recognizing these nuances is essential in appraising the efficacy of these online platforms as mental health support systems.

As this study transitions into the discussion, we don't just synthesize these critical insights but will also delve into their wider implications.

5. Discussion

5.1 Comparative Cultural Dynamics across Subreddits

The thematic analysis across these subreddits illustrates distinct patterns of user engagement and community behavior. In r/depression, themes like 'Emotional Disclosure' and 'Story Sharing' dominate, indicating a community deeply engaged in personal narratives and empathetic exchanges. This suggests a digital manifestation of community support where shared experiences and coping strategies form a complex tapestry. Similarly, r/Anxiety focuses on 'Resilience and Coping Strategies' and 'Resource Sharing,' reflecting an active engagement in mutual support and anxiety management strategies. However, the limited emphasis on anonymity in these discussions might indicate an underexplored dimension in the discourse of online mental health support.

Anonymity on Reddit, while facilitating openness in discussions, appears more as an implicit backdrop rather than a focal feature. This observation diverges from the perspectives of authors like Van der Nagel & Frith (2015) or , Choudhury & De (2014) who assert that anonymity is a central keystone for users of Reddit, crucial for the growth of these online communities. While their assertion is undoubtedly valid, the findings of this research suggest a nuanced understanding. Anonymity, while present, is almost not actively mentioned or foregrounded by users in these mental health subreddits. This implies that users might not consciously consider anonymity as a primary enabler for sharing their experiences. Instead, it seems that other factors, such as shared experiences and the community ethos, play a more significant role in fostering the communal dynamics observed in these subreddits. This contrast indicates that while anonymity is a foundational aspect of Reddit, its role as a conscious driver of user engagement and community building in mental health contexts may not be as predominant as previously thought.

5.2 Moderation and Implications for Digital Mental Health Discourse

In regard to moderation and community dynamics, the work of Saha et al. (2020), highlights the importance of moderation in creating safe spaces for mental health discourse on Reddit. The thematic analysis shows low rates of moderator intervention, suggesting a self-regulating community where norms are upheld by users themselves. This observation points to a mature community dynamic where moderation is less about intervention and more about guiding and maintaining a supportive environment. This finding can inform future research on the evolving role of moderators in online communities, particularly in how they balance intervention with fostering self-regulation.

The comparative analysis across the subreddits unveils different interaction cultures, mirroring the diverse needs of their members, which aligns with the work of Park & Conway (2018) and Dai & Shi (2022), who claim that different online communities exhibit unique interaction cultures, depending on various factors such as the community ethos, moderation practices and user demographics.

r/depression, with its focus on emotional disclosure and venting, offers a supportive space for those dealing with depressive states, while r/Anxiety facilitates more solution-oriented discussions. r/MentalHealth's broad approach suggests a balance between practical advice and a space for

expressing various mental health challenges. These dynamics highlight the distinct ways online platforms can support mental health discourse, each tailored to the specific needs of their community.

These insights have significant implications for understanding digital mental health discourse. They reveal the potential of online platforms in fostering supportive communities and facilitating shared understanding, as well as emotional and informational support. However, the potential risks of echo chambers in r/Depression and the lack of deeper emotional engagement in r/Anxiety suggest limitations in these forums. This points to a need for strategies that balance empathetic support with constructive mental wellness pathways.

To enhance the depth and specificity of support in these online communities, future research could explore the impact of anonymity in greater detail and examine the role of moderators in shaping community interactions. Understanding how different moderation styles affect community dynamics and the creation of safe spaces for mental health discussions could provide valuable insights.

6. Conclusion

6.1 Synthesis of Online Mental Health Community Dynamics

In exploring the dynamics of social interaction within mental health subreddits on Reddit, this thesis has unearthed a complex tapestry of emotional disclosure, story sharing, and resource sharing, painting a vivid picture of the unique social support systems that exist in these digital sanctuaries. These subreddits serve not only as platforms for sharing experiences but also as crucial spaces for empathy and mutual understanding among individuals facing mental health challenges.

The research undertaken in this thesis has illuminated the transformative role of online platforms, specifically Reddit's mental health subreddits, in offering a new paradigm for mental health support. These digital spaces have evolved beyond their initial function as mere platforms for communication, emerging as vital lifelines where empathy, understanding, and support are actively nurtured and fostered. The study delved into the unique dynamics of these online communities, uncovering how the community-driven aspects of such platforms create an environment conducive to openness and vulnerability. Unlike traditional mental health settings, where individuals may feel constrained by social norms or privacy concerns, these online spaces allow users to express themselves freely, share personal experiences, and seek advice without fear of judgment or stigma.

This level of candid interaction is further enhanced by the global reach of these platforms, transcending geographical and social barriers. Users from diverse backgrounds and with varied experiences come together, contributing to a rich tapestry of perspectives and support mechanisms. This collective understanding, built on shared experiences and empathetic interactions, forms a robust support system that operates on principles of mutual aid and communal support.

Moreover, this thesis significantly enriches the existing body of literature on digital mental health interventions. By closely examining how mental health subreddits function as de facto support groups, the research bridges a critical gap in our understanding of the dynamics and efficacy of online mental health communities. The insights gained from this study extend beyond academic relevance, offering practical implications for a range of stakeholders, including mental health professionals and policymakers. For mental health professionals, these findings suggest new avenues for integrating online platforms into traditional therapeutic models, providing a complementary approach to mental health care. Policymakers can use this knowledge to inform guidelines and regulations that support and enhance the effectiveness of digital mental health interventions.

Reflecting on the research problem, the study acknowledges the potential challenges inherent in digital platforms, such as misinformation and the risk of echo chambers. The methodology was effective in unraveling these complex dynamics. However, it also highlighted the necessity for more comprehensive research methodologies to fully grasp the potential and address the challenges of these digital sanctuaries.

6.2 Future Trajectories and Implications for Mental Health Support

Future research directions are manifold and crucial. Developing guidelines for moderating mental health discussions online is imperative to ensure these platforms remain safe and supportive. Investigating the long-term effects of participation in these communities on individual mental health could provide deeper insights into their therapeutic value. Additionally, exploring how digital platforms can address mental health issues across different cultures and demographics is essential to ensure inclusivity and accessibility in mental health support.

In essence, this thesis heralds a new perspective on the future of mental health support—a future that is increasingly digital, community-driven, and inclusive. It underscores the critical importance of recognizing online mental health communities as legitimate and effective venues for mental health care, challenging traditional perceptions of mental health interventions. Emphasizing the role of digital communities in mental health care, the study advocates for the integration of traditional and digital approaches to ensure mental health support remains accessible, inclusive, and adaptable to the diverse needs of a global population. By acknowledging the potential of these platforms to provide accessible and adaptable support, this research calls for a reevaluation of strategies in the digital age, advocating for a broader integration of digital approaches alongside conventional methods. In the rapidly evolving landscape of mental health care, the implication is clear: digital platforms play a crucial role in meeting diverse needs across the globe, paving the way for a more holistic and inclusive approach to mental health and well-being.

7. Bibliography

Bryant, Antony, and Kathy Charmaz. *The SAGE Handbook of Grounded Theory*. 1
Oliver's Yard, 55 City Road, London England EC1Y 1SP United Kingdom: SAGE
Publications Ltd, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848607941>.

- Charmaz, Kathy. *Constructing Grounded Theory: A Practical Guide through Qualitative Analysis*. SAGE, 2006.
- Chuang, Tyrus, and Rabindra Ratan. 'Discord Use and Intent'. *Journal of Student Research* 11, no. 3 (31 August 2022). <https://doi.org/10.47611/jsrhs.v11i3.3795>.
- Dai, Yue (Nancy), and Jingyuan Shi. 'Vicarious Interactions in Online Support Communities: The Roles of Visual Anonymity and Social Identification'. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 27, no. 3 (23 March 2022): zmac006. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcmc/zmac006>.
- De Choudhury, Munmun, and Sushovan De. 'Mental Health Discourse on Reddit: Self-Disclosure, Social Support, and Anonymity'. *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media* 8, no. 1 (16 May 2014): 71–80. <https://doi.org/10.1609/icwsm.v8i1.14526>.
- Giles, David C., and Julie Newbold. 'Self- and Other-Diagnosis in User-Led Mental Health Online Communities'. *Qualitative Health Research* 21, no. 3 (March 2011): 419–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732310381388>.
- Glaser, Barney G., and Anselm L. Strauss. *The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203793206>.
- Huh, Jina, Rebecca Marmor, and Xiaoqian Jiang. 'Lessons Learned for Online Health Community Moderator Roles: A Mixed-Methods Study of Moderators Resigning From WebMD Communities'. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 18, no. 9 (8 September 2016): e247. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.6331>.
- Lester, Jessica Nina, Yonjoo Cho, and Chad R. Lochmiller. 'Learning to Do Qualitative Data Analysis: A Starting Point'. *Human Resource Development Review* 19, no. 1 (March 2020): 94–106. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484320903890>.
- Luo, Mufan, and Jeffrey T. Hancock. 'Self-Disclosure and Social Media: Motivations, Mechanisms and Psychological Well-Being'. *Current Opinion in Psychology* 31 (February 2020): 110–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2019.08.019>.
- Martin, Vivian B., Clifton Scott, Bonnie Brennen, and Meenakshi Gigi Durham. 'What Is Grounded Theory Good For?' *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly* 95, no. 1 (March 2018): 11–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077699018759676>.
- Park, Albert, and Mike Conway. 'Harnessing Reddit to Understand the Written-Communication Challenges Experienced by Individuals With Mental Health Disorders: Analysis of Texts From Mental Health Communities'. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 20, no. 4 (10 April 2018): e121. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.8219>.
- Pfeil, Ulrike, and Panayiotis Zaphiris. 'Applying Qualitative Content Analysis to Study Online Support Communities'. *Universal Access in the Information Society* 9, no. 1 (March 2010): 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-009-0154-3>.
- Prakasam, Naveena, and Louisa Huxtable-Thomas. 'Reddit: Affordances as an Enabler for Shifting Loyalties'. *Information Systems Frontiers* 23, no. 3 (1 June 2021): 723–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-020-10002-x>.

- Pretorius, Claudette, Derek Chambers, Benjamin Cowan, and David Coyle. 'Young People Seeking Help Online for Mental Health: Cross-Sectional Survey Study'. *JMIR Mental Health* 6, no. 8 (26 August 2019): e13524. <https://doi.org/10.2196/13524>.
- Rayland, Amy, and Jacob Andrews. 'From Social Network to Peer Support Network: Opportunities to Explore Mechanisms of Online Peer Support for Mental Health'. *JMIR Mental Health* 10 (28 February 2023): e41855. <https://doi.org/10.2196/41855>.
- Saha, Koustuv, Sindhu Kiranmai Ernala, Sarmistha Dutta, Eva Sharma, and Munmun De Choudhury. 'Understanding Moderation in Online Mental Health Communities'. In *Social Computing and Social Media. Participation, User Experience, Consumer Experience, and Applications of Social Computing*, edited by Gabriele Meiselwitz, 87–107. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49576-3_7.
- Skousen, Tanner, Hani Safadi, Colleen Young, Elena Karahanna, Sami Safadi, and Fouad Chebib. 'Successful Moderation in Online Patient Communities: Inductive Case Study'. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 22, no. 3 (17 March 2020): e15983. <https://doi.org/10.2196/15983>.
- Timonen, Virpi, Geraldine Foley, and Catherine Conlon. 'Challenges When Using Grounded Theory: A Pragmatic Introduction to Doing GT Research'. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods* 17, no. 1 (1 December 2018): 160940691875808. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406918758086>.
- Tongco, Ma. Dolores C. 'Purposive Sampling as a Tool for Informant Selection'. *Ethnobotany Research and Applications* 5 (31 December 2007): 147. <https://doi.org/10.17348/era.5.0.147-158>.
- Van Der Nagel, Emily, and Jordan Frith. 'Anonymity, Pseudonymity, and the Agency of Online Identity: Examining the Social Practices of r/Gonewild'. *First Monday*, 22 February 2015. <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v20i3.5615>.
- Wise, Kevin, Brian Hamman, and Kjerstin Thorson. 'Moderation, Response Rate, and Message Interactivity: Features of Online Communities and Their Effects on Intent to Participate'. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 12, no. 1 (October 2006): 24–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2006.00313.x>.
- Xu, Ronghua, and Qingpeng Zhang. 'Understanding Online Health Groups for Depression: Social Network and Linguistic Perspectives'. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 18, no. 3 (10 March 2016): e63. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.5042>.

8. Appendix

A. Research Limitations and Contextual Notes

1. Demographic Limitation of Reddit Users

- Source: "Reddit's Manosphere and the Challenge of Quantifying Hate"
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/20563051211019004>
- Note: Acknowledgement of the limitation that most Reddit users are young males, impacting the generalizability of the findings.

2. Data Extraction Tool

- Python Script: Accessible at
https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1auMyaG6ojW4C93AzemWG_HpF2PWh7IYc?usp=sharing
- Description: Explanation of the script used for data extraction, including its functionality and output format.

3. Subreddit User Base Dynamics

- Observation: Significant growth in the member count and monthly post amount of the studied subreddits since September 2023, suggesting dynamic, evolving communities.

B. Analytical Process and Observations

1. Keyword Analysis Methodology

- Explanation: Details on the creation of filters for counting keywords and the rationale behind excluding certain words like "I" for their lack of analytical value.

2. User Participation Patterns

- Observation: Recognition of highly active users who were identified in more than half of the posts, indicating a presence of core, engaged community members.

3. Moderation Analysis Challenges

- Methodology: Description of the process and limitations encountered in analyzing the frequency of post and comment deletions by moderators.

- Specific Findings: Documentation of instances where posts were deleted by moderators or users, along with the number of such posts in r/depression and r/Anxiety.
- URL Review: Details about checking post URLs for active status and handling of deleted posts.

4. Links to Studied Subreddits

r/depression: <https://www.reddit.com/r/depression/>

r/mentalhealth: <https://www.reddit.com/r/mentalhealth/>

r/Anxiety: <https://www.reddit.com/r/Anxiety/>

5. Accuracy and Bias in Analysis

- Acknowledgement: Admission of the potential for biased interpretation and lack of absolute accuracy in the manual analysis and categorization of posts and comments.